

PRIETO, Heloísa. **Coração musical de bumba-meu-boi** [“Musical heart of Bumba meu boi”]. Illustrations Jô Oliveira. São Paulo: Estrela Cultura, 2018.

REVIEW¹

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Secrets of violeiros and horse riders, adventures to the sound of serenades. In this book, acclaimed writer Heloisa Prieto takes up the Bumba meu boi heritage and embarks on an exploration of literary works by Brazilian writers Mário de Andrade and Guimarães Rosa. Brazilian folklore resurfaces with its legends and myths in the captivating illustrations by renowned artist Jô de Oliveira. This book brings together, therefore, two masters of the literature for children and young adults.

Keywords: Tradition. Regionalism. Folklore.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2019 Bologna. Books published in 2018 and reviewed in 2019. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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